

Communication and Dissemination Plan
WP5: Communication and Dissemination and demonstration

D 5.1: Communication and Dissemination Plan

Authors: Emma Lönn and Thomas Börjesson

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Document Information

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Lead Author	Emma Lönn
Co - Authors	Thomas Börjesson
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TABLE 1: DOCUMENT INFORMATION

¹ PU = public | PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services) | RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services) | CO= Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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TABLE 2: DOCUMENT HISTORY

Abbreviations

EC	EUROPEAN COMMISSION	WP	WORK PACKAGE
GA	GRANT AGREEMENT	GAS	INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS
EU	EUROPEAN UNION	OG	OPERATIONAL GROUP
EIP	EUROPEAN INNOVATION PARTNERSHIP	AKIS	AGRICULTURAL KNOWLEDGE INFORMATION SYSTEM
CDS	COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY	CAP	COMMON AGRICULTURAL POLICY
KPI	KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATOR		

TABLE 3: ABBREVIATIONS

Participants

Participants		Contact
Agricultural University of Athens (AUA) Greece		Prof. Spyros Fountas sfountas@aual.gr
University of Santiago de Compostela (USC) Spain		MOSQUERA LOSADA MARIA ROSA mrosa.mosquera.losada@usc.es
University of Pisa (UNIPi) Italy		Daniele Antichi daniele.antichi@unipi.it
Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies (LLU) Latvia		Jānis Jaško janis.jasko@llu.lv
SK ADAS LTD (ADAS) UK		Lynn Tatnell, Will John Lynn.Tatnell@adas.co.uk will.john@adas.co.uk
AGROVÄST Livsmedel AB (AGROVAST) Sweden		Thomas Börjesson thomas.borjesson@agrovast.se
Institut Français de la Vigne et du Vin (IFV) France		Eirios Hugo, Camille Guilbert eirios.hugo@vignevin.com camille.guilbert@vignevin.com
Farmers Parliament (ZSA) Latvia		Inga Berzina inga@zemniekusaeima.lv
Organic Research Centre (ORC) UK		Katie Bliss katie.b@organicresearchcentre.com
AGROMET P.C. (AGROMET) Greece		Aris Zamidis azamidis@tractorgps.gr

TABLE 4: PARTICIPANTS

Document summary

This document contains a plan for the communication and dissemination that will be performed in the project Oper 8: European Thematic Network for unlocking the full potential of Operational Groups on alternative weed control. It has received grants under the topic Horizon-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-23, grant agreement No 101060591, – Broaden EIP Operational Group outcomes by means of thematic networks, compiling and sharing knowledge ready for practice.

It summarizes the communication and dissemination strategy and goals as well as a detailed description of the tools and activities that are going to be used. It also contains a timetable for producing the materials needed to fulfill the goals.

It is divided in 3 sections, the first contains a description of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy, the second describes the tools and the target groups, while in the third section, a work plan for the activities is summarized.

The plan will be discussed as the project progresses and it will be formally updated annually.

Limitations: This plan is not considering the internal communication within the project, only external communication. However, tools discussed are also useful for internal spread of information, although this is not the main purpose.

Document content

Part. 1 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

1.1 Introduction

The Communication and Dissemination Strategy includes a general description about the main aim of the communication and dissemination plan and the ways that the plan will be more effective. Moreover, the objectives of CDS will be reported in relation to the target audience. This section describes the principles and goals, the products and deliverables that will be the subject of the dissemination activities.

1.2 Communication and Dissemination definitions

Within Oper-8 consortium both communication and dissemination activities will be undertaken at consortium and at partners' level. While both start at the outset of the project and continue throughout its entire duration until the very end, "communication" aims to promote the project and its results, whereas the objective of "dissemination" is to transfer the project's knowledge and results by all appropriate means. According to European IPR Helpdesk the definitions of these activities are:

1. Communication: "Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange"
2. Dissemination: "The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium"

1.3 Background and purpose

The plan will describe the strategy as well as how the communication will be organized both internally and externally and the different target groups as well as the different tools that are going to be used in the communication activities. The plan will be regularly monitored and evaluated and if necessary updated in close conjunction with all project partners. The evaluation will be based on a Balanced Score Card (BSC). The cooperation within the EU-community such as the CAP-network, EIP-AGRI, other EU-projects and networks such as EUREKA will be strongly emphasized. The tools will be adapted to suit the different target groups identified and according to local differences.

Effective dissemination and communication are about using more than one medium and combining different tactical tools in order to reach all stakeholders and objectives, all planned in a strategic manner. In Table 5, an outline of which activities that are placed in the foreground during the lifetime of the project is illustrated.

1st year	2nd-3rd year		After the project
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning launching Communication Actions • Preparation of basic communication materials • Website and social media in place 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of communication strategies • Social networks • Stakeholder workshops, conferences and webinars • Demonstrations • Podcasts, e-learning tools, videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement of communication strategies • Social networks • Scientific publications • Press releases • Stakeholder workshops • Demonstrations • Podcasts, e-learning tools, videos 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social networks • Scientific publications • Press releases • Stakeholder workshops

TABLE 5: CORE ACTIVITIES DURING THE PROJECT'S LIFETIME

1.3.1.1 The overall strategy will rely on the following key principles:

1.	Customization of dissemination material: starting from pan-European dissemination materials produced in English, a translation into the native languages of the project partners will be made to increase effectiveness of the dissemination strategy.
2.	Oper-8 project will exploit the extroversion of its partners and their strong presence in the international research community through their systematic participation in knowledge dissemination actions
3.	Communication will be addressed to multiple audiences (farmers, advisors, industry, researchers, policy makers, consumers) and the broad public emphasizing on new products quality, health and environmental benefits.
4.	Multiplier and network effects will be leveraged to maximise the impact of dissemination activities: In this respect, the complementary competences of the Oper8 project partners will allow the impact of the CDS and Communication and Dissemination Activities to be multiplied beyond the initial actors to a wide range of stakeholders (farmers, food industry, retailers, consumers, researchers, and academia) targeted by the dissemination activities.
5.	The entire chain of economic, environmental and health benefits of the Oper8 practices and products will be taken into account i.e., starting from the field to food industry, food safety experts, advisors, academics, along to consumers

TABLE 6: KEY PRINCIPLES

1.4 Communication and Dissemination Objectives

- Effective communication both internally and externally
- Ensure that the project assets are fully exploited
- Raise awareness and extend visibility of the project to key stakeholders
- Make the relevant insights, lessons learnt, and relevant data generated available for key stakeholders
- Reach policy makers and equip them with appropriate policy options and recommendations to promote sustainable and resilient agriculture
- Use appropriate tools for the different target groups
- Reach the indicators set up
- Set up a strategy to cooperate with other EU-bodies
- Set up rules for how to handle external communication
- Set up frequencies for updates and production of different dissemination materials

Knowledge transfer between academia and industry is bidirectional: innovative OG solutions and research results will be passed to industry, while industrial validation will serve as feedback to academia to inspire new ideas and ways of tackling the problems in a more effective and practical way. Thus, the partners will seek to collaborate closely in the period after the project to achieve scientific and commercial benefits.

The developed OG solutions will ensure new and lasting collaborations among Oper8 partners and will lead to the self-sustainability of the partnership after the project end. The outcomes of Oper8 applied within the agricultural production, can also be used in a wide range of applications in Europe and worldwide, that can keep the partnership active after the end of the project.

Raise awareness among the CAP networks and policy makers on the importance of employees (current and next generation) training for a more inclusive and efficient uptake alternative weed solutions and more sustainable agricultural practices.

Encourage involvement of stakeholders and AKIS actors, generating their understanding and obtaining their support for reaching potential customers and end-users.

The Oper8 CDS is focused, clear and continuous, avoiding one-time and piecemeal actions and functioning as a practical toolkit, providing the appropriate means to ensure efficient visibility of the project activities and dissemination of its outputs

throughout its life cycle, at the same time as promoting stakeholder involvement. The strategy will be treated as a living document, and it will be reviewed and adapted during the project on a regular basis, in accordance to the results of the different activities, the dissemination needs of the individual partners and the opportunities that may emerge. The strategy will support project partners in maximising the impact of their individual activities, while ensuring the sustainability of project results as a whole and the continuation of the collaboration among project partners and between partners and stakeholders.

1.4.1.1 We think that the keys to effective communication are the following:

- Activity carried out in a timely manner.
- Information must be accurate – control measures must be in place.
- Close coordination with other EU-bodies
- Appropriate activities considering:
 - Time spent
 - Timing
 - Excepted impact
- Tailor-made information for different target groups.

An effective contingency plan in case that the communication and dissemination outcome does not reach the target values will be set up. The dissemination manager is responsible for this, see section 3.1.1. Not only quantitative measures but also a judgement on how effective the dissemination activities will be monitored as described in section 3.1.2.

Part. 2 Communication and Dissemination Materials and Tools

2.1 Dissemination portfolio

All dissemination messages as well as the overall design will be tailored to take into consideration the target audience and context of the institution or country in question and will be integrated into different tools.

- Oper8 website
- Social media
- Development of Promotional materials
- Newsletters
- Workshops
- Scientific publications
- Seminars
- Final Conference

The way in which Oper8 will be perceived from the targeted audience will be a consequence of the outcomes and the communication of these outcomes. Therefore, a consistent and positive image has to be created, by using corporate brand identity. The image created here will build trust and responsiveness from the project partners, and other key stakeholders. Building a corporate identity aims to facilitate the use of certain graphic and visual parameters by all the participants by following guidelines and templates. Depending on the effect you want to achieve, you choose the way you will convey your message. Sometimes informing is enough - a one-way process of telling or explaining how something is. Then an article on the intranet and/or external web or an email may be the right channel. To create understanding, commitment and to have an effect, communication is needed - a two-way process. Then meetings and dialogue are also needed, sometimes repeatedly.

Summary of the expected objectives, most important impact and target audiences are listed in Table 1 and a more comprehensive description of the different tools are listed below.

Dissemination Action	Indicator	Objective	Target Audience/ Expected Impact	Contingency plan
Social media presence (LinkedIn, Facebook Twitter)	Number of posts in social media during project lifetime: 360	Short communication on news, events etc.	Farmers, Advisors, Industrial and Technological communities/ Generate awareness of the project, its expected results and benefits	Increase partners' dedication to publications in social media
Conferences and webinar	Number of consumer/technical conferences and webinars: 70	Better understanding of the project activities, feedback from audience	Scientific Community, R&D&DI stakeholders, Food Industry, General Public and Authorities/ Communicate Oper8 results, Raise awareness in the public	Responsibilities and budget have been assigned, Supervise training team, promotional materials in place

Project Website	Number of monthly visits to the portal: 600	Overview, most important source both for quick glance and to get in-depth information about the project	Stakeholders in the areas of food processing, food quality/safety, EU and International SMEs, co-operations and Associations & general public/ Generate awareness, inform on project's progress	Promoting the web site in Social Networks, keep it up to date.
Publications	Number of scientific papers published during project lifetime: 60	Summarize new findings, encourage further research in the field	Scientific, industry and R&D&I stakeholders/ Increase interest and disseminate the results of Oper8 in both academia and industry	Increase partners' dedication to redaction of reports
Project Leaflets, Brochures	Number of distributed printed/digital materials: 20000	Increase the spread of the project, reach a wide range of audiences	Stakeholders in the areas of food processing, food quality/safety, EU and International SMEs, co-operations and Associations & general public/ Generate awareness, inform on project's progress	Responsibilities and budget have been assigned. Supervise training team
Workshops, Seminars	Number of demonstration workshops: 24	Engage the audience in a more profound way than on conferences, feedback	Students, ESRs and ERs, Industry stakeholders, R&D&I key players/ Contribute to knowledgebase, motivate researchers, promote results of Oper8, increase networking and exchange of ideas	Responsibilities and budget have been assigned. Supervise training team

TABLE 7: MEASURES OF THE IMPACT OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

2.1.1 Visual Identity Handbook

A logo compatible with the project theme has been created. Along with it, identity colours have been identified and will be used for all materials that will be available for the public. The logo and corporate colours have also been the basis for all templates to be used by the consortium internally: deliverables, power point presentations etc.

Figure 1: Oper8's logotype

In particular, all communication and dissemination material will showcase the Oper8 logo, the EU emblem, and a clear statement that the project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, through the following text:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101606591

Oper8 partners will develop deliverables, reports and presentations which, in most cases, will be submitted and made available to different audiences. A part for the scientific publications will use the template provided by the publisher and all the other documents produced will use Oper8's templates. The dissemination team has developed both a Word template and a PowerPoint template that have been stored to the project's repository for further use by the project's partners. The first will be used for reports and deliverables and the second will serve for presentations, both at events and for internal consortium meetings. The templates were designed in line with all the communication and dissemination materials of Oper8, in order to support the uniformization of reports (Word template) and public presentations (Power Point template). The templates for text documents such as deliverables and letters (Microsoft Word) and presentations (Microsoft PowerPoint) are available. Samples of the templates are presented in Annex.

2.1.2 Website

The main communication tool of Oper8 project will be the website (www.oper-8.eu) with the core function of being the natural gateway to both get an overview of the project and to search for in-depth information. The website was developed at the beginning of the project and contains general static information about the project (aims & objectives, partners description, work packages, etc.), as well as dynamic information that will be updated as they happen (news, events, etc.).

Information about the project, such as deliverables, promotional material (brochure, leaflet, poster, etc.), publications and videos will be available for downloading. Additionally, easy access to the project's social media profiles is provided. The website will also be used to link to the database of solutions provided by the project.

The Oper8 Digital Inventory will be created and managed in WP2 and will have its own tab in the website menu, with a direct link to this platform. The digital inventory is seen as an inventory for all solutions and content created within the project, linking to previous and related projects. Its creation will commence in M6. The digital inventory will consider the inputs collected from the needs, gaps and barriers survey (T2.1) and meetings regarding Oper8 and its expectations. It will also make connections to other H2020 and European projects such as NEFERTITI (<https://nefertiti-h2020.eu/>), Imparadise (<https://iwmpraise.eu/>) and IPM Works (<https://ipmworks.net/>).

The website will be managed by AGROVAST and will be updated regularly with the collaboration of all the partners. It will be aligned with following principals:

- Usability. Clear and accessible structure.
- Updated. At least ones a month an update will be made.
- Accuracy. Content will be relevant for the target groups.

The working language will be English and for all materials uploaded, at least an English summary need to be provided. We aim for everything to be translated from English into Swedish, French, Latvian, Spanish, Greek and Italian. The visitors at the website will be counted. We will also monitor from which country, which page they visit and for how long.

All partners can upload, but it need to be checked and accepted by AGROVAST before it is uploaded.

Structure of the website will be as follows:

Start	About us	What we do	News	Media	Contact
<p>Here it should be short and interesting information about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "About us" - "What we do" - "News" - "Media". <p>All of these will link on to the respective page.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social Media - Newsletter signup 	<p>A landing page that links to deeper information in a subpage about the items below?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information about you behind the project? - Why is the project important? - The idea behind it? - What is the purpose? 	<p>A landing page about the project itself that links to deeper information in a subpage?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Methods? 	<p>All news posted here are displayed. They can be sorted into categories, etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Categories? - File? - Tags? - Search? 	<p>A landing page that links to the respective subpage.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Podcast? - Videos? - Images? 	<p>Here we list the different ways to get in touch with Oper8.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contact information? - Social media? - Map? - Newsletter signup?

Figure 2: The sitemap for www.oper-8.eu

Indicators: Visits- at the website: 20.000

2.1.3 Social media: Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn

The core functions for the social media:

- Attract farmers and entrepreneurs in the green sector to get interested in searching information from the website, subscribe from newsletters, take part in DEMO-events, learn from videos, podcasts, e-learning modules etc.
- Get feedback from different target groups.

Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/people/Oper-8/100086344463846/
Twitter	https://twitter.com/OPER8_EU
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/oper-8/

TABLE 8: SOCIAL MEDIA PROFILES

Oper8 project since its beginning on October 2022, has a presence on the most popular social networks, i.e. Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn. The strong presence of Oper8 on social media will contribute on its communication strategy to reach a broad audience.

Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn are particularly suitable, for community management and to address the target group through visual and interactive content. These social networks are also suitable for companies, primarily to stimulate discussion and interaction

AGROVAST is the administrator of the social media accounts and is responsible to upload posts related with the project, answer messages, and confirm posts and comments. An email address has been created dedicated to the project (++) linked to administrator email in order to ensure direct communication with the audience. Also, AGROVAST will be in close collaboration with the

Oper8 partners in order to publish the latest news from all partners and inform the followers about upcoming events. A digital inventory of all upcoming events will be maintained by each partner. The inventory will be checked every 3 weeks, to identify events that require promotion and/or preparation of communication and dissemination materials.

Additionally, AGROVAST is responsible for the monthly monitoring of the social media presence, by using different indicators for each social media network. These indicators will be presented and analysed on Deliverable D5.2 on M24 and on the intermediate reports of Communication and Dissemination Actions created in an annual base.

The first posts on the project’s social media pages were posted in early October 2022. In the upcoming period the social media accounts will be updated preferably every week.

Indicator of number of posts altogether during the project lifetime: 120 posts in each of the social media by partners.

Indicator: Number of followers: 2000 for each of the platforms Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn.

2.1.4 E-newsletter

An e-newsletter regarding the progress of the project, the achievements, outcomes, events, secondees interviews, hosting institutions presentations will be released in annual base. The e-Newsletter will be uploaded on the website of the project and will be communicated through Oper8 social media. The release schedule is described in the table below. Additionally, the Oper8 partners will be encouraged to forward the e-newsletter to their network and their own communication channels.

Core function: Up to date information about activities in the respective OGs, in 7 languages.

New letter number	2023	2024	2025
1	28 February	28 February	28 February
2	31 May	31 May	31 May
3	31 August	31 August	31 August
4	30 November	30 November	

TABLE 9: E-NEWSLETTER RELEASE SCHEDULE DURING THE YEARS 2023-2025

Indicator: 3500 recipients.

2.1.5 Videos

Core function: Hands-on information on how the different tools work. Primary target groups: Advisors and Farmers.

Typical situation to produce video at DEMO-events. Quality control important, quality criteria will be set up. Can be in different languages, always with at least English as subtitle (French, Spanish).

Indicator: 50 videos will be produced.

2.1.6 Podcasts

Core function: Get the project known to a broader public.

Sent on local radio, native language.

Indicator: 1 each year for each OG.

2.1.7 Promotional material

Core function: To be used at fairs, exhibitions, etc.

Could be leaflets, booklets, banners, posters, roll-ups depending on what is suitable at each individual event.

Indicator: 20.000

2.1.8 Fact sheets, EIP-AGRI Practice Abstracts

Core function: Hands-on information on the different techniques. Target groups mainly farmers and advisors.

Indicator: 80/100

2.1.9 Press-releases

Core functions: Advertise workshops, demo-events. In native language.

Indicator: 30

2.1.10 Publications

Core function: Comprehensive information about the techniques, progress during the project.

Core target groups: Researchers and Policy makers.

Communication will to a large extent be organised within the EU-community such as <https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/horizon-magazine>. During the first year of the project, no scientific publications are foreseen.

Indicator: 60 of which 3 will be scientific.

2.1.11 Demonstrations and cross-visits

Core function: Peer-peer learning, hand-on training. Spread best practices and promoting peer-to-peer learning

All target groups are encouraged to come, but particularly important to attract farmers/advisors.

Indicator: On-farm-demonstrations organised: At least 24 in all partner countries.

2.1.12 National and European Workshops

Core function: To get feedback from AKIS actors, to adjust future activities according to stakeholders needs and interests. All target groups are encouraged to come, essential to have inputs from different groups. Can be arranged together with DEMO-activities.

Indicator: 280 attendants.

2.1.13 Training material, including e-learning material

Core function: Complement newsletters, demos, videos with more in-depth material. Can be in the form of webinars or face to face training courses. Webinars and e-learning materials should be available through the website. Translated to 7 languages.

Indicator: in total 2100 users.

2.1.14 Conferences, events and fairs

Core function: Reach a large number of stakeholders, farmers etc., with at least short messages about the project. Communicate project achievements using the promotional material.

Receive feedback from all target groups.

Indicator: Participation in 70 events.

2.1.15 Final Oper8 event

Core function: Communicate project results with a wide range of policymakers and cross-border networks.

Indicator: 1 held in Brussels

2.2 Messages and target audience

The Oper8 project will communicate different kinds of results (knowledge, routines, models, processes, products etc.), and the target groups for each of the results will also be variable. To increase effectiveness of the message it is important to identify the relevant differences between the potential user groups so that the tailored information is effective, using specific dissemination channels to different target groups.

A preliminary distinction can be made between:

1. Target Users – the ones that will make direct use of project outputs;
2. Project Stakeholders – the ones who, although not directly involved in any project activity, share an interest in the success of the initiative (local government, university rectorate and administrative staff, local companies, etc

For the communication to be successful, you need to relate to the target group's interest, knowledge and commitment to the topics and issues you want to communicate.

For an effective realization of each activity, it is crucial to clearly understand who the targeted subjects for the communication are. Therefore, key audiences were already identified in the proposal stage in order to plan the dissemination activities. In general, target groups are entities and/or individuals that can potentially benefit from the project results.

- Farmers, Farmers' Associations
- Food Industries, Unions, food industry's employees' associations and federations.
- Agri-food sector Researchers, Technology Providers, Consultants, Technical Chambers
- Consumers as individuals, Consumers' Associations
- Broader Society stakeholders, Local communities
- Others: experts on regulatory issues related to food safety; policy makers at European and national level in the areas of agri-food sector technologies and practices.

It is important to define the following:

- What is it that you want to communicate? How does the message differ depending on target group?
- Often there are several target groups, and the message then needs to be adapted in terms of content and appeal. Prioritize what is particularly important for your target group, for the business and for the employees so that what your communication becomes relevant.
- Main message: What is the most important thing you want to get across? What is the bottom line that all your target audiences touch on?

In Table 10, target groups are listed along with the goals for the communication and examples of relevant tools to be used

Target Group	Communication approach/key tools	Expected impact/feedback
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Farmers	Approach mainly through social media. Raise interest in taking part in DEMO -events, learn more through website, sign up for newsletters, learn about the techniques through videos, pods-casts E-learning tools	Raise awareness of alternative weed control measures Higher uptake of innovative solutions Feedback: Barriers for adopting the techniques. Solutions not seen yet.
Advisory groups	Approach mainly through website, in-depth learning materials accessed through the website. Newsletters on specific OGs.	Increase knowledge in general about alternative weed control measures. Increase knowledge about the OGs in the project. Feedback: Barriers, specific for different solutions, recommended adjustments. Knowledge/technologies sought for
SMEs technology providers, entrepreneurs in the green sector	Website, gain interest through social media. In depth description of the OGs	Promote cooperation's between companies with complementary skills Complement with story telling on alternative solutions for reducing herbicide use
Stakeholders along the food chain National Networks CAP-networks	Website, facts sheets, newsletters Links to partners, networks, EU-bodies	Awareness of the range of solutions. Contribute to a shift in attitudes. Market considerations Obstacles in reaching consumers Storytelling
Public authorities incl. Policymakers	Website, fact sheets, newsletters, in-depth description of the different methods.	Awareness of the range of applications available to reduce the use of herbicides Promote and encourage EU-strategies to reduce the herbicide use
Research	Website, in-depth descriptions of the different methods	Awareness of the different methods provided as well as their potential. Increase contacts between research and advisors/farmers. Increase attention from young researchers on alternative weed control measures.
Consumers, public	Website, social media	Increase awareness of alternative control measures and that the AKIS community is making efforts to minimize the use of herbicides. Get feedback via social media.

TABLE 10: TARGET GROUPS, COMMUNICATION APPROACH, KEY COMMUNICATION TOOLS, EXPECTED IMPACT AND FEEDBACK FROM THE TARGET GROUPS

Part. 3 Communication and Dissemination Activities and Work Plan

The overall dissemination activities will focus on the use of interactive internet means such as websites, social media (e.g., LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter), and e-newsletters, publication of articles and scientific papers, but most importantly targeted events, like conferences, workshops or fairs where the target audience can be addressed face-to-face, and interaction would be facilitated.

During all phases of the project the project partners are committed to use a consistent and uniform approach for all materials and presentations where dissemination for Oper8 is foreseen. Conflict of interest and IPR (Intellectual Property Rights) sensitive information will always be monitored by the project responsible dissemination and communication manager.

Events (e.g., workshops, conferences), either organised by Oper8 or with the participation of Oper8 partners, are essential for creating strong impact on the community of stakeholders. The organisation of or the participation in events provide the project the opportunity to: share the various research and experimental results from the project activities; exchange information with target groups, stakeholders and other projects; increase the visibility of the project and generate wider impact. All Oper8 partners will identify event opportunities to disseminate the project and its actions.

Oper8 communication and dissemination work plan envisages a series of actions that will minimize the impact of such inhibitory situations in the performance of the planned CDS.

- Regular review and update of OPER8 website – Check if the site carries the right messages reflecting the current stage of the project’s development. Make sure that information is presented in a clear and informative manner, that all partners are listed, that project’s vision is clearly stated, that event details are correct and that all public deliverables are posted. Upload useful to the visitor’s material such as flyers, brochures, video clips or infographics.
- Be active on social media
- Prepare and disseminate e-newsletters in regular base
- Organization of virtual events, podcasts and webinars to engage with the project’s prospects.

3.1 Communication and Dissemination Governance

All the OPER8 partners are experienced in the implementation of EU-funded projects and are committed and aware on the importance of the communication and dissemination on such projects. Thus, all partners will rely on their accumulated communication and dissemination experience and tools in order to achieve the highest impact of the project.

AGROVAST is the leader of WP 5, but all partners will be engaged on the on-going communication and dissemination of the project. Thus, AGROVAST will mainly play a coordinator/facilitator role, ensuring that the “Communication and Dissemination Plans” is collectively implemented by all partners. CDS will be implemented by all partners under the guidance and supervision of the Dissemination Manager.

For the project to have a real impact it is necessary that all partners involved are committed to disseminating OPER8. As such, it is expected that all OPER8 partners will work together in the following manner:

- All activities coordinated be AGROVAST in close cooperation with representatives from all partners.
- All partners need to be engaged in the communicative activities.
- By regularly filling in the document “Dissemination activities” in which all planned dissemination activities are going to be filled in. It is crucial that they are communicated as soon as they are known, to allow for timely production of dissemination materials.
- By introducing the project to their network of contacts and stakeholders (posts on all social media accounts with the official logo and description of the project);
- By sharing and reposting through their own channels all OPER8 publications on the project’s social media as well as to share OPER8 press releases, newsletters and specific content through their network and newsletters subscribers;
- By contributing, whenever requested, to the participation in interviews or providing clarifications and quotations that can be shared in the project’s channels;
- By sharing directly with the Dissemination Manager all the scientific papers produced under OPER8, as well as all events/initiatives in which they participate (before, to be announced, and after, to be reported)

- By translating the contents whenever the partners wish to disseminate the materials in a language other than English. Partners will perform the necessary translation, no external service for this.
- By contributing to making an analysis of each communication situation. Typical questions to pose are:
 - What is to be communicated?
 - What is known by the audience already?
 - What challenges and opportunities exist?
 - What other processes internally or externally are going on that you may need to consider or benefit from?
 - What demarcations should be made?

As the OPER8 coordinator is aware of the scientific work that is being developed and the results that are being produced, the coordinator will select the contents that considered appropriate for dissemination. These contents will be shared with AGROVAST, once approved by the coordinator. Technical information shall be transmitted by AGROVAST in the most succinct and understandable way, so that summaries and infographics to be developed based on this information and disseminated to the general public.

3.1.1 Dissemination Manager

This role will be assigned to Emma Lynn from AGROVAST.

Her role will be the following:

- Planning and coordination of communication and dissemination activities
- Reporting communication and dissemination activities, compiling the information received from partners annually
- Website content management: news & events, library
- Social media community manager: Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn
- Edition of digital newsletters with the contribution from the partners
- Coordination of the promotional materials design, layout and printing
- Coordination of the publication of popular articles on partners' media and in specialised magazines
- Elaboration of project-related press releases and coordination of local press releases
- Coordination in collaboration with project co-ordinator of the programme and logistics of the Oper8, workshops, webinars, and Final Conference
- Setting up a contingency plan in case the target values for the objectives are not reached.

3.1.2 Monitoring and Reporting

All the dissemination and communication activities will be registered through an efficient monitoring and reporting process. All partners will be responsible to report the activities they are involved into the Dissemination Manager (e.g., participation in an event, publication, press releases etc.). For this purpose, a specific process will be established within the consortium that requires partners regularly indicate all dissemination and communication activities they have carried out. A spreadsheet will be created and shared with all the partners to collect that information. Partners are required to complete the monitoring spreadsheet periodically (i.e., every six months), and indicate their partner name, the type of dissemination/ communication action, the channel or media used, as well as the date, the type of reach, the type and number of audiences reached, and evidence of the activity (e.g., picture, link, news piece, etc.). The spreadsheet will contain two different sections to include broad dissemination activities (social media posts, generic publications and others) and scientific publications. AGROVAST will be responsible for ensuring that this information is properly collected. Moreover, AGROVAST will have a similar spreadsheet where all the data retrieved from the partners will be collected in order to create the intermediate reports of Communication and Dissemination Actions in an annual base.

Furthermore, in order to measure the impact of the project and carry out an accurate evaluation of the dissemination and communication activities, both quantitative and qualitative indicators must be considered. Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and respective target values have been defined for the various tools and channels proposed as part of the dissemination and communication plan. KPIs relevant for WP 5 are listed in Table 11. Measuring these indicators on a regular basis is important to understand if the progress is being made or if additional measures must be implemented to ensure target values are met.

The impact of the dissemination and communication efforts will be regularly analysed, following both quantitative and qualitative review.

KPI	Target Value	Deliverable
Number of links with other EU/National projects	15	5.2
Number of views of Practice abstracts, Fact sheets and audio/visual materials	10000	5.2
Number of stakeholders enrolled in e-learning module	200	5.2
Number of stakeholders reached through communication channels	30000	5.2

TABLE 11: KPI'S RELEVANT FOR WP5

3.2 Timeline

Communication and Dissemination activities will run throughout project's lifetime, which is 36 months. Activities at the beginning of the project include the development of the project's visual identity and the design of the CDS. These have already been completed. Publications on social media channels will be regular and the website will be updated in monthly base. A first version of dissemination material has been designed. A timeline for the implementation of Communication and Dissemination activities is presented below. Most of the actions will be conducted during the lifespan of the project. Oper8 partners will follow this plan as much as possible. The plan is, however, flexible enough to accommodate any necessary change that seems beneficial for a greater project visibility and impact.

In general, for Wp5: Meetings will start with be held once a week, till things have set and as a routine later on, meetings will be held once every third week. In the following a timetable with more details for the first few months of the project. Details on podcasts, e-learning tools, promotional materials etc. will be discussed during the WP-meetings.

Meetings will normally be held on Teams.

3.2.1 Task 5.1 Communication & Dissemination plan

Activity/item	Responsible/active partner(s)	Due	Action
First Draft of the plan	AGROVAST	16 Dec 2022	Send to all partners for comments/revision
First Draft of the plan	ALL PARTNERS	21 Dec 2022	Comments either in share point, email or Teams site
Second Draft of the plan	AGROVAST	21 Dec 2022	Send to all partners for comments/revision
Second Draft of the plan	ALL PARTNERS	23 Dec 2022	Comments in
Third draft of first version of the plan	AGROVAST	26 Dec 2022	Plan delivered to AUA
Third Draft for first version of the plan	AUA	28 Dec 2022	Comments returned
Final first version of the plan	AGROVAST	30 Dec 2022	Plan delivered
Comments for revised plan	ALL PARTNERS	30 Nov 2023	On Wp5 workshop/Teams etc.
Draft for revised plan	AGROVAST	6 Dec 2023	Send to all partners for comments/revision in Teams
Draft for revised plan	ALL PARTNERS	13 Dec 2023	Comments returned

Draft for revised plan	AGROVAST	13 Dec 2023	Sent to AUA
Draft for revised plan	AUA	19 Dec 2023	Comments delivered to AGROVAST
Final revised version of the plan	AGROVAST	31 Dec 2023	Plan delivered, D5.1
Comments for revised plan	ALL PARTNERS	30 Nov 2024	On Wp5 workshop/Teams
Draft for revised plan	AGROVAST	6 Dec 2024	Send to all partners for comments/revision in Teams
Draft for revised plan	ALL PARTNERS	13 Dec 2024	Comments returned
Draft for revised plan	AGROVAST	13 Dec 2024	Sent to AUA
Draft for revised plan	AUA	19 Dec 2024	Comments delivered to AGROVAST
Final revised version of the plan	AGROVAST	31 Dec 2024	Plan delivered
Comments for revised plan	ALL PARTNERS	30 Nov 2023	On Wp5 workshop/Teams etc.
Draft for revised plan	AGROVAST	6 Dec 2023	Send to all partners for comments/revision in Teams
Draft for revised plan	ALL PARTNERS	13 Dec 2023	Comments returned

TABLE 12: TASK 5.1 COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION PLAN

3.2.2 Task 5.2 - C&D materials and tools

Activity/item	Responsible/active partner(s)	Due	Action
Visual Identity Handbook: Logo, templates, trademark, typography	AGROVAST	21 Dec 2022	Ready
Website: First version	AGROVAST	16 Dec 2022	Ready
Second version including short description of the different OGs, links to partners etc.	ALL PARTNERS	21 Dec	Inputs
Second version including short description of the different OGs, links to partners etc.	AGROVAST	3 Jan 2023	Ready
Third version	AGROVAST/ALL PARTNERS	13 Jan 2023	Discussed on WP meeting
Third version	AGROVAST	17 Jan 2023	Ready
Third version	AGROVAST	20 Jan 2023	Discussed on WP meeting
Continuous uploading of news on website	AGROVAST	At least once a month	Discussed at the WP 5 meetings that are going to be held with an interval of three weeks
Electronic newsletter	AGROVAST	13 Jan 2023	Discussion on Wp5 meeting, draft sent out
First newsletter in English	ALL PARTNERS	18 Jan 2023	Contributions to Agroväst
First Newsletter in English	ALL PARTNERS, AGROVAST	20 Jan 2023	First version set on meeting, published
First Newsletter translated to 7 languages	ALL PARTNERS	25 Jan 2023	Ready, uploaded

Report upcoming events	ALL PARTNERS,	Before each WP 5 meeting	Upcoming events are listed in spreadsheet
Report upcoming events	AGROVAST	At each WP 5 meeting	Spreadsheet with upcoming events is presented and compared with target values of participations
List of indicative events 2023	ALL PARTNERS	13 Jan 2023	Possible participation in events 2023 discussed
List of indicative events 2023	AGROAST/ADAS	20 Jan 2023	List presented on meeting, discussed
Promotional materials	ALL PARTNERS, ADAS, AGROVAST	16 Dec 2022	Discuss need for promotional material for upcoming events
Social media	AGROVAST, ADAS, AUA	13 Dec 2022	News posted to advertise upcoming events
Social media	ALL PARTNERS	16 Dec 2022	Discuss procedure for reporting news and structure for translation etc.
Social media	AGROVAST	20 Dec 2022	Procedure for uploading thing on social media set
Social media, continuous posts of news	ALL PARTNERS	Jan 2023 onwards	According to set routine, posts will in general be out once a week, if there are things to communicate
Introductory Communication video	ALL PARTNERS	16 Dec	Discuss content, production, translation etc for the communication video
Introductory Communication video	AGROVAST	13 Jan 2023	Proposal presented
Communication, Dissemination and Demonstrations report	AGROVAST	30 Sep 2023	Report delivered, D5.2
Communication, Dissemination and Demonstrations report	AGROVAST	30 Sep 2024	Report delivered, D5.2
Communication, Dissemination and Demonstrations report	AGROVAST	30 SEP 2025	Report delivered, D5.2

TABLE 13: TASK 5.2 – C&D MATERIALS AND TOOLS

3.2.3 Task 5.3 - Links with EIP-AGRI and EU-initiatives

Activity/item	Responsible/active partner(s)	Due	Action
Contact with EIP AGRI service point	ADAS, AGROVAST	16 Dec 2022	Article in EIP Agriinnovation Magazine, discuss on meeting
Choice of links to EU-networks and projects that that should be on future versions of the website	AGROVAST/ALL PARTNERS	16 Dec. 2022	Discussion on meeting
Routines for future contacts with EU-networks and projects	AGROVAST/ALL PARTNERS	16 Dec 2022	First discussion on meeting
Routines for future contacts with EU-networks and projects	AGROVAST/ALL PARTNERS	13 Jan 2023	Continued discussion
Established links	AGROVAST	31 Dec 2023	Reported in Delivery 5.2.

TABLE 14: TASK 5.3 – LINKS WITH EIP-AGRI AND EU-INITIATIVES

3.2.4 Task 5.4 - Demonstration activities through peer-to-peer learning towards AKIS actors

Activity/item	Responsible/active partner(s)	Due	Action
Demo activities.4	ADAS/ ALL PARTNERS	4	Partners to discuss plans. Every 3 weeks meet to discuss progress. Focussed meetings Early March, September each year

Demo activities	ADAS/ ALL PARTNERS	6	Discuss plans, advertising and filming of demos
Each OG to complete 3 Demo activities	ALL PARTNERS	M1-12	All planned events to be communicated in advance to AGROVAST for promotion and preparation of C&D materials. Each partner is responsible for recording aspects of the event for results to be shared with a wider audience after the event. Number of attendees should be gathered to determine impact
Review meeting for Year 1 Demo activities	ADAS/ ALL PARTNERS	12	All partners to summarise and review Year 1 demos and start planning year 2 demos
Plan Year 2 demos	ADAS/ ALL PARTNERS	16	Partners to discuss plans for year 2 demos and how to advertise them
Each OG to complete 3 demo events	ALL PARTNERS	M12-24	All planned events to be communicated in advance to AGROVAST for promotion and preparation of C&D materials. Each partner is responsible for recording aspects of the event for results to be shared with a wider audience after the event
Review meeting for Year 2 Demo activities events	ADAS/ ALL PARTNERS	24	All partners to summarise and review Year 2 demos and start planning year 3 demos
Plan Demo activities Year 3 demos	ADAS/ ALL PARTNERS	28	Partners to discuss plans for year 3 demos and how to advertise them
Each OG to complete 3 demo activities events	ALL PARTNERS	M24-36	All planned events to be communicated in advance to AGROVAST for promotion and preparation of C&D materials. Each partner is responsible for recording aspects of the event for results to be shared with a wider audience after the event
Review meeting for Year 3 demonstration events	ADAS/ ALL PARTNERS	34	All partners to summarise and review Year 3 demos and discuss outcomes
Dissemination of 80 fact sheets and 100 practise abstracts on Oper8 website, social media, newsletters and EIP-AGRI service point	AGROVAST/ ALL PARTNERS	M1-33	USC to provide material for dissemination when produced. AGROVAST to prepare dissemination routes on the website and social media. All partners are responsible for sharing the resources within national networks
Sharing 50-audio visual materials and one e-learning module produced by WP4 on Oper8 website, social media, newsletters and EIP-AGRI service point	AGROVAST/ ALL PARTNERS	M1-34	USC to provide material for dissemination when produced. AGROVAST to prepare dissemination routes on the website and social media. All partners are responsible for sharing the resources within national networks

TABLE 15: 5.4 – DEMONSTRATION ACTIVITIES THROUGH PEER-TO-PEER LEARNING TOWARDS AKIS ACTORS